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TOLERANT EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AS A REQUIREMENT FOR THE FORMATION OF THE PROFESSIONALLY IMPORTANT SKILLS OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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The article explores the problem of the formation of professional tolerance of future specialists in education. An analysis has been made of scientific psychological and pedagogical literature devoted to the subject of the research. The concept of “professional tolerance of teacher” is defined, its essence is revealed. The diagnosis of the formation of professional tolerance of future teachers on the basis of the author’s express method “Diagnosis of the formation levels of teachers’ professional tolerance” has been carried out. The level of professional tolerance of future teachers has been found to be insufficient. Discussions are under way to establish professional tolerance in higher educational institution in a specially created tolerant educational environment. The essence of the concept of “tolerant educational environment” is considered. Approaches, patterns and principles of building a tolerant educational environment were highlighted. A number of characteristics of a tolerant educational environment has been defined. The existence of a tolerant educational environment is defined as one of the basic conditions for the formation of future specialists’ professional tolerance.

Keywords: *professionally important skills, tolerance, professional tolerance, tolerant educational environment.*

MEDIUL EDUCAȚIONAL TOLERANT CA O CONDIȚIE ESENȚIALĂ PENTRU FORMAREA COMPETENȚELOR PROFESIONALE ALE VIITORILOR SPECIALIȘTI ÎN CADRUL INSTITUȚIILOR SUPERIOARE

În articol este abordată problema privind formarea toleranței profesionale la viitorii specialiști din instituțiile educaționale. În baza analizei literaturii de specialitate din domeniul psihologiei și din cel al pedagogiei a fost definit conceptul „toleranță profesională” la cadrele didactice, fiind clarificată esența acestuia. Autorii propun o metodă de investigare a toleranței profesionale, în baza căreia a fost realizată o cercetare privind nivelul de formare a toleranței profesionale la viitorii profesori, studiul demonstrând un nivel insuficient de dezvoltare a acestei competențe la cadrele didactice în formare. În acest sens, în articol este pus în discuție factorul de bază care ar contribui esențial la formarea toleranței profesionale în instituțiile superioare – un mediu universitar tolerant. Astfel, este definită esența conceptului „mediu educațional tolerant”, fiind determinate caracteristicile acestuia în instituțiile universitare, inclusiv sunt evidențiate condițiile și principiile pentru crearea unui asemenea mediu. Se argumentează că existența unui asemenea context educațional este condiția de bază în vederea formării toleranței profesionale la viitorii specialiști.

Cuvinte-cheie: *competențe profesionale importante, toleranță, toleranță profesională, mediu educațional tolerant.*

Introduction

The training of future specialists in education at a qualitatively new level is an important priority of the State and one of the most important stages of personal growth in the process of which professionally important skills are formed, meeting the needs of society on the basis of highly skilled labour and universal values. Professionally important skills are the individual dynamics of the personality, the individual mental and psychomotor skills (expressed by the level of development of the corresponding mental and psychomotor processes), and the physical skills, meeting the requirements of a particular profession and contributing to the successful attainment of that profession [1]. One of these skills is professional tolerance, which poses important challenges to modern higher education.

An analysis of the practice has shown that the professional skills available for higher education do not always meet the high standards required by modern science. Higher educational institutions have a significant educational impact on future researchers, purposefully and systematically influencing the development of their self-awareness. Therefore, it is the educational space of higher education that can become the place where future specialists can learn a new pattern of behaviour – professional tolerance.

The main purpose of professional tolerance is to acquire a personality in which there is a spirit of partnership, respect and a positive attitude to the human dignity of others [2]. Higher education should help future teachers

to understand and adopt the moral values that would enable them to act in the best possible way for humanity, which they would carry through their lives, and were able to pass it on to the next generation [3]. Higher educational institutions have an important task to prepare not only a qualified specialist in a particular field, but also a person with professional tolerance.

In the context of our research, we understand the teachers' professional tolerance as a complex of professionally important skills of personality, which ensure efficiency in professional activity and are characterized by active life and professional position, which manifests itself in respect for another person as an equal; the ability to accept different thoughts, values, behaviours, external characteristics; the willingness to enter into an equal partnership with all participants in the educational process on the basis of moral standards, responsible and yet flexible interaction with them, preserving their own values and individuality [4]. The necessary skills are formed around professional tolerance, it creates a personal orientation, a system of relationships, determines the choice of behaviour strategies and motivates the development of certain skills and, is therefore a tool for the successful self-realization of future specialists [5].

Thus, the development of professional competencies is a topical and key issue in the development of a psychological framework for the training of future specialists. One of the most important tasks of the educational system is the creation of an educational environment and the promotion of tolerance as a professional quality of future teachers.

Sample and method

In order to determine the level of professional tolerance of future specialists we have developed the author's express methodology "Diagnosis of the formation levels of teachers' professional tolerance" [4]. *The development of the authorised express methodology* was carried out in several stages, meeting the basic psychometric requirements, and providing for validation and reliability of the methodology. The following tasks have been carried out in the process of designing the express method: the most complete set of questions has been drawn up, the set of answers to which makes it possible to determine the level of professional tolerance in teachers by component and in general, the method chosen for processing the results of the methodology, the scale of the response measurement, the sample selected for testing the methodology, standardization and validation of the developed methodology. The test has made it possible to assert that the express method can be described as an independent diagnostic tool that measures sufficiently reliably the levels of professional tolerance of teachers.

The study was carried out in higher educational institutions. The total sample size is 250 future education specialists from different regions of Ukraine. Mathematical statistics and data analysis was performed using SPSS (version 20.0)

Results and discussion

The results of the empirical research made it possible to determine the levels of professional tolerance of future specialists (Table).

Table

Level of professional tolerance among leaders of future education professionals

Formation level	Respondents (%)
Low	25.8
Medium	63.1
High	11.1

As can be seen from Table 1, the level of professional tolerance of the subjects under investigation has been insufficient. Thus, the majority of respondents have a low (25.8%) and medium (63.1%) level of professional tolerance, which makes future specialists unstable to numerous occupational stresses, negatively affects interaction with participants in the educational process, jeopardizing the achievement of a successful professional career. And only in 11.1% of the respondents there was a high level of professional tolerance. It ensures an active attitude in the professional activity and an a priori positive attitude towards employees and the environment, respect for and tolerance of others, their thoughts and behaviour, it is manifested in the intransigence of all kinds of inhuman acts and in the very positive way of humanizing education.

The problems identified makes it necessary to develop the professional tolerance of future teachers, which, in our view, can be implemented in the process of vocational training (higher education). We believe that the development of the future specialist as an individual in higher educational institution is influenced by the educational environment and by interaction with fellow students, senior or junior students and teachers. The educational environment of higher education can be defined as a holistic social and psychological space encompassing a set of conditions, relationships formed through interpersonal interaction, a system of goals, intentions, communication and information, which play an educational role as well as organized pedagogical influences, processes [6].

In the vocational educational system, a tolerant educational environment is a set of conditions necessary for the free development of the personality in the educational process and for fostering tolerance among participants in the process as a professional skill is of particular importance. In this environment social experience is formed and developed, future specialists learn to accept complex life phenomena, the manifestations of social and material stratification are reduced, and a humanistic orientation is formed [7]. Future teachers learn about the system of values and norms of stereotypes in society, and they develop a system of internal regulations and habitual norms of behaviour. In this space, future specialists not only adapt to life and social environment, but also become creators of their life, transform themselves into self-fulfilling [8].

The creation of a tolerant educational environment is based on the principles of humanization, integration, variability and flexibility, as well as on humanistic ideas in personal theories, and considers its development to be a fulfilment of the human need for self-realization, those who understand the importance of favourable relationships between the subjects of the educational process and through the creation of conditions for freedom, emotional well-being, positive motivation and creativity [9]. By changing a person's behaviour and individuality, but leaving the environment unchanged, we gain temporary successes, do not solve the problem of creation of a professional tolerant personality [10].

The scientific approaches underlying the creation of a tolerant educational environment – civilisational, sociocultural, action-oriented, system-synergistic – presuppose the training of the future specialist in accordance with the requirements of ecological civilization for life in the world, to live in an ethno-group, to live in a professional group, to live in harmony with their spiritual world; includes applicants for higher education in joint activities to form a tolerant environment [11]. Patterns and principles deriving from approaches that determine the orientation of the educational process towards the development of a professionally tolerant personality, characterizing a tolerant environment and its resistance to influences and changes, both from within and from outside, make it possible to implement variations in the educational process, both in content and in the use of modern psychological and pedagogical technologies. The principles underlying the building of a tolerant educational environment derive from these three patterns: multiculturalism, multi-ethnicity, additionality, affinity, unity in the content of educational and other activities, and environmental conditionality, universality, implementation of the subject-matter interaction and educational dialogue [12]. A tolerant educational environment is based on values such as personal responsibility for one's actions, personal initiative, high professionalism, subordination to professional culture, orientation to organisational values, autonomy of thought, independence of conduct in the organisation, subjective and tolerant relations, trust in professional and personal relations, cooperation and mutual respect, self-control over the conformity of their actions and actions with the tolerant norms.

The characteristics of a tolerant educational environment, namely:

- openness (openness to different beliefs, confessions and nationalities; openness to critical dialogue, interpersonal and group communication; there are tendencies to expand and strengthen its interaction with life, all social and educational institutions of life);
- multiculturalism and multiethnicity;
- integrity (it is this characteristic, which is objectively inherent in the phenomena of the human world, that should determine the structure of the educational process and thus characterise the educational environment);
- multidimensionality (understanding and studying the phenomenon from different perspectives);
- educational background versatility (equipping higher educational applicants with universal means of action to extract and process new knowledge that may be required to meet unknown challenges; the versatility of education is always linked to its fundamental nature, making it possible to identify the most important patterns of phenomena and processes of reality described in classical and new scientific theories);

- coverage (maximum coverage) required for higher educational applicants to choose the content and mode of education according to their needs and objectives (implementation of a varied educational process, both in content and in educational technologies, which undoubtedly gives it a highly tolerant character);
- communicative orientation (the process of transmitting knowledge, the medium of transmission, the language, can be seen as a field, uniting all educational environments);
- comparison (is the social background for comparing and self-actualising the individual; it is important from the point of view of the possibility of enhancing the capacity of the educational environment to develop tolerance).

We dedicate two mechanisms to the development of a tolerant educational environment. The first is the cessation of negative, aggressive or hostile reactions to the other (certain restrictions described in the rules, statutes and other regulations of the higher educational institution, with responsibility for intolerant behaviour). Unfortunately, such restrictions express a minimum level of respect for others, and if it fails, individuals and society slide towards intolerance and human rights violations. Another mechanism to organise and strengthen a tolerant environment is the creation of the conditions necessary for the exercise of human rights and the establishment of democracy. These mechanisms are not competitive but complementary, depending on the situation [13].

Thus, within the educational space of a higher educational institution, the creation of a tolerant environment means fostering relations of openness and mutual responsibility, empathy and mutual assistance; recognition of diversity; developing the ability to recognize injustices and take steps to overcome them; the ability to constructively bridge differences and move from conflict situations to reconciliation and conflict resolution; group reflexes that reflect an understanding of the diversity of behaviour.

Conclusions

A tolerant educational environment is based on humanistic and moral values, creates conditions for the development of an inter-subjective educational process against the background of current changes in the personality and is a condition for humanistic education; developing and nurturing a professionally tolerant individual with adequate self-esteem, highly developed self-identification mechanisms. In higher education, the influence of a tolerant educational environment on the formation of professional tolerance is exercised through identification, imitation, persuasion and conformance.

The development of effective ways to foster professional tolerance among the younger generation of our State poses an increasing challenge to researchers. Bearing this in mind, we believe that it is possible to use the results of this study to develop a model for the creation of professional tolerance among students of higher education in the process of vocational training.

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